

Liberty University

Luke-Eyewitness: are the “many” - in Luke 1:1 - Old Testament Prophets and Scribes?

A Research Paper Submitted in Partial Fulfillment for the Degree of Master of Arts in Christian
Apologetics

Rawlings School of Divinity

by

Leo C. Donofrio, J.D.

Theology 525: Systematic Theology 1, Professor Nathan Hermann

June 27, 2024

Contents

Thesis Statement	3
Introduction	3
Part 1: “who from the beginning were eyewitnesses and ministers of the word”	7
Part 2: Circular exegesis concerning the <i>many</i> blocks Luke as eyewitness	11
Conclusion	13
Bibliography	14

Thesis Statement

A rational translation of Luke’s preface (Luke 1:1-4), designed to remove linguistic contradictions and notorious ambiguities noted therein, must consider whether the “many” (πολλοὶ - *polloi*), referred to in Luke 1:1, were *not* Christian authorities prior to Luke, but rather Old Testament eyewitnesses of ancient scriptural events, their scribes, and scroll attendants, so that “the beginning” (ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς - *ap’ archēs*) of Luke 1:2 goes all the way back to Genesis, while “from the first” (ἀνωθεν - *anōthen*) in Luke 1:3 refers back only to the birth of Christ, thereby removing an insurmountable obstacle preventing a much earlier date for Luke’s Gospel.

Introduction

Forasmuch as many have taken in hand to draw up a narrative concerning those matters which have been fulfilled among us, even as they delivered them unto us, who from the beginning were eyewitnesses and ministers of the word, it seemed good to me also, having traced the course of all things accurately from the first, to write unto thee in order, most excellent Theophilus; that thou mightest know the certainty concerning the things wherein thou wast instructed (emphasis added) (Luke 1:1-4, American Standard Version).

Luke’s preface has confounded Christian scholarship for two thousand years, as “classic rivers of ink have been poured out over [it].”¹ Yet, there is no consensus² regarding its translation or vocabulary, which has been consistently described as ambiguous by important scholars, such as H.J. Cadbury, who published upon it extensively³ in the early twentieth century, and Loveday

¹ Matteo Crimella, “‘That You May Know’. The Preface to Luke’s Gospel (Lk 1:1–4),” *Biblica et Patristica Thoruniensia* 13, no. 4 (2021): 367, <https://doi.org/10.12775/BPTh.2020.017>.

² For a comprehensive review of the magnitude of disagreement concerning virtually every word in Luke’s preface, see: James W. Scott, “Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem.” PhD diss., St. Andrews University, 1985, <https://research-repository.st-andrews.ac.uk/handle/10023/14101>.

³ H.J. Cadbury, "Commentary on the Preface of Luke" [Appendix C], in *The Beginnings of Christianity, Part i: The Acts of the Apostles*, ed. F.J. Foakes-Jackson and K. Lake (New York: Macmillan, 1920-1933) 2489-2510;

Alexander, whose monumental tome examining the prologue's specific genre may be the most extensive work of scholarship ever devised to penetrate the mysterious veil of Luke's Gospel:

“Despite its long-recognized linguistic ambiguities, the preface has been widely accepted as an indication that Luke's ideals at least approximated to those of ancient and modern historians alike. The almost complete critical consensus on this point is bolstered by the observation, made by a number of critics around the beginning of the twentieth century, that the style and construction of the preface, as well as its vocabulary, are reminiscent of prefaces found among the ancient historians.”⁴

Alexander's thesis concluded that Luke's preface was not pure historiography, rather, she determined it was specifically intended to convey that a scientific⁵ treatise would follow. But despite her exhaustive efforts which have been praised as, “The monograph that has left the greatest mark on critical discussion of the Lukan preface,”⁶ her conclusions have been largely disputed by scholars; such as John Moles who determined the preface was styled after a Greek decree designed to support Lukan superiority concerning both historiography and Christian doctrine⁷; Zachary Dawson, who thwarted both Alexander's and Moles' conclusions, holding that Luke's opening, “displays features conventional to prefaces of historiographical writing...and is not layered with additional rhetorical meaning”⁸; and Matteo Crimella, who tackled, “the complex philological problems of the text in order to highlight the strategies

"The Knowledge Claimed in Luke's Preface," *The Expositor* 8, no. 24 (1922) 401-420; "The Purpose Expressed in Luke's Preface," *The Expositor* 8, no. 21 (1921) 431-441.

⁴ Loveday Alexander, *The preface to Luke's Gospel*, Cambridge University Press (1993), 2.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 142.

⁶ Matteo Crimella, “That You May Know’,” 368.

⁷ John Moles, “Luke's Preface: The Greek Decree, Classical Historiography and Christian Redefinitions.” *New Testament Studies* 57, no. 4 (2011): 461. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0028688511000154>.

⁸ Dawson, Zachary K. “Does Luke's Preface Resemble a Greek Decree? Comparing the Epigraphical and Papyrological Evidence of Greek Decrees with Ancient Preface Formulae,” *New Testament Studies* 65 no. 4 (October 2019): 552, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002868851900016X>.

employed by the narrator,”⁹ in deducing that Luke intended the preface to signal a written verification of Christian theology offered to a catechumen named Theophilus.¹⁰

So, the aftermath left in the wake of Loveday Alexander’s valiant work has, rather than clarifying Luke’s preface, unfortunately contributed to perpetuating its infamous reputation for esoteric ambiguity.

Luke’s preface, though only one sentence long, is comprised of four terse verses, with virtually every word having been comprehensively investigated by scholars going all the way back to the patristic fathers. Cadbury perfectly sized up the frenzied scholarship surrounding the prologue as follows:

In the study of the earliest Christian history no passage has had more emphasis laid upon it than the brief preface of Luke. It is the only place in the synoptic gospels where the consciousness of authorship is expressed, containing as it does the only reference outside the gospel of John to the origin or purpose of the evangelic record. It has naturally been repeatedly treated in special monographs, as well as in introductions and commentaries, and has been cited in connection with every problem of early Christian literature. This importance, together with the difficulties which its terse and ambiguous language raises, justifies a somewhat extended commentary, especially in connection with a work like Acts which is written by the same author and addressed to the same person.¹¹

While this paper does not address Cadbury’s conclusion that the same author wrote both, Luke and Acts, a subject he also provided celebrated historical scholarship upon¹², the thesis herein does not require both books to be by the same author. This paper concerns only Luke, and it will demonstrate that, as far as the actual text is concerned, there is a potential translation of the preface, which does not appear to have been previously considered by published scholarship,

⁹ Matteo Crimella, “‘That You May Know,’” 367.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 390.

¹¹ H.J. Cadbury, "Commentary on the Preface of Luke", 489.

¹² Henry J. Cadbury, *The Making of Luke-Acts*, S.P.C.K. (1958).

that avoids the most vexatious contradictions giving rise to all of the *perceived* ambiguities scholars have previously encountered.

Despite the noted exegetical frustrations of New Testament scholars, there is one aspect of the preface all previous scholarship agrees upon: that the *many* Luke referred to in his first verse are exclusively Christian authorities prior to Luke¹³.

Our research has not revealed any prior scholarship challenging such consensus, or even suggesting this paper's challenge thereto, which is this: The *many* are not prior Christian authorities, authors, or scribes, but rather those authors who wrote the books of the Old Testament, based upon eyewitness testimony of prophets, kings, and other participants, the records of which were handed down, from generation to generation, by scribes, and attendants of the scrolls, concerning the fulfillment of prophecy by the Word of God, going all the way back to "the beginning" first mentioned in Scripture at Genesis 1:1, whereas the author of Luke, perhaps a highly educated Jewish disciple of Jesus¹⁴, having been an eyewitness to Christ from the start of His ministry at the time of His baptism, through the miracles, crucifixion, resurrection, and ascension, felt called, like previous servants of God, to provide an accurate account, to the temple authorities, the Jewish nation, and the rest of the world, concerning the fulfillment of prophecy in Jesus Christ, the long expected Messiah.

There is a virtual¹⁵ singularity of consensus in Christian scholarship that the author of Luke was not an eyewitness to Christ¹⁶. This is because it is almost unanimously held by scholars that

¹³ For example, neither Loveday Alexander's tome, nor James W. Scott's thesis, have even a scintilla of suggestion otherwise. See: Loveday Alexander, *The preface to Luke's Gospel*, Cambridge University Press (1993); and, James W. Scott, "Luke's Preface and the Synoptic Problem."

¹⁴ See note 15 below.

¹⁵ J.W. Wenham is the only contemporary scholar to suggest that Luke was an eyewitness to Christ, and that he was one of the seventy disciples chosen by Christ: J.W. Wenham, "Gospel Origins," *Trinity Journal* 7, no. 2, (Fall 1978): 112.

¹⁶ James W. Scott, "Luke's Preface and the Synoptic Problem," 75.

the *many* were Christian authorities who handed down their writings, and, or, oral traditions,¹⁷ to Luke, which he later collated and redacted into the Gospel¹⁸. But that is not what the text of the preface actually says, and to make that consensus assumption fit, scholars are forced to grope around in the dark, failing, after two-thousand years, to cure the vexatious ambiguities such consensus creates. Whereas the thesis of this paper removes all linguistic contradictions perpetrated upon the text by circular¹⁹ pre-conceived notions that Luke was not an eyewitness to Christ, which are not based on proofs found in the other Gospels, or writings of the patristic fathers proving unique knowledge outside of the actual Gospel texts. The circular manifestation that Luke only received the Gospel from other Christian authorities, rather than directly from Christ, may be the actual disease perpetuating confusion, with the notorious ambiguities being just a symptom of that prognosis.

It is the humble purpose of this paper to introduce the suggestion of its thesis, so that the noble work of Christian scholars may expand to consider whether Luke was an eyewitness to, and early disciple of, Christ's ministry, and that the Gospel bearing his name may be of a much earlier date than the current consensus suggests.

Part 1: “*who from the beginning were eyewitnesses and ministers of the word*”

Before examining whether the *many* were not Christian authorities prior to Luke, it is paramount to discern the two time periods specifically placed into the text; the first being, ἀπ’

¹⁷ Ibid., ii-iii.

¹⁸ Ibid., 203.

¹⁹ See Part 2, below.

ἀρχῆς - *ap' archēs*, always translated without controversy as, “the beginning” (Luke 1:2); and the second, ἀνωθεν - *anōthen*, often translated as, “from the first” (Luke 1:3), while there is much controversy surrounding this term.²⁰

There are only two options: either two separate time periods are intended by the author; or, one time period is intended, with each literary expression reflecting only a redundant point of style pertaining to that same time period, as was noted by James W. Scott, (in what we have found to be the most comprehensive exegetical discussion of each word in Luke’s preface (prior to the work of Loveday Alexander), in his PhD dissertation, *Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem*, (St. Andrews University, 1985)), who addressed the problem of translating *anōthen*, as to have the same exact meaning as *ap' archēs*: “It would be redundant for him to say that he has understood them all ‘from their beginning.’”²¹ Hence, the two terms should relate to different time periods.

The most important scholarship concerning our paper’s thesis directly flows from two stunning footnotes in Scott’s dissertation, both of which concern, ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς (Luke 1:2), universally translated as *the beginning*: “According to A. M. Pope...Luke has the entire course of history in view (for ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς in vs. 2 recalls Gen. 1:1!), all the events of which ‘had come to their fruition’ in the flowering of Christianity.”²² Incredibly, neither Pope, nor Scott (nor any other scholar our research could find), apply Pope’s suggestion as a guide to consider whether the *many* from Luke 1:1 might be Old Testament parties to Scripture, despite Pope’s suggestion that *the beginning* in Luke 1:2 refers back to Genesis 1:1.

Remarkably, there was a second chance in Scott’s dissertation to reconsider the *many* again, just a few pages later, when he cites Pope in the second crucial footnote reiterating, and elaborating, the same exact point:

²⁰ James W. Scott provides ample proof of the controversy surrounding the proposed translations of, ἀνωθεν - *anōthen*, in his dissertation, using thirty-four pages to do so; “Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem,” 112-146.

²¹ James W. Scott, “Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem,” 133.

²² *Ibid.*, 376; citing, A. M. Pope, “The Key Word of the Lucan Narratives,” *The Canadian Journal of Religious Thought* 3 (1926): 47-48.

Pope (in "Key Word," 48-49), interpreting "from the beginning" as a reference to the Creation, and "the word" as a reference to the mind of God revealed in history, goes on to imagine that among the servants of the word Luke "may be including those Greek philosophers and poets, who, all unknown to themselves, were preparing the way of the Lord."²³

I find it absolutely mind-boggling that Pope takes such a strange turn. Just as he gets over the target concerning the *many*, his pre-conceived notion of Luke as a gentile Christian, and not a Jew, leads him to the following assessment:

“The only Gentile contributor to the literature of the Bible claims that Jesus has come, not merely to fulfil the religious hopes of the Jewish people, but to reveal His unique relationship to universal history. In his preface, Luke sets over against the eye-witnesses from the beginning...and among these he may be including those Greek philosophers and poets, who, all unknown to themselves, were preparing the way of the Lord.”²⁴

How does Pope not apply the same logic anywhere in this article to the *many* in Luke 1:1? That the *many* might have been Old Testament participants, rather than Greek philosophers and poets, surely must take precedence if “the beginning” goes back to Genesis, but such exegesis is nowhere to be found in Pope’s article, Scott’s thesis, the work of Alexander, Cadbury, or any other scholar we could find.

Pope’s thesis was that the Gospel of Luke was an apologetic to defend Christianity from Roman persecution, so that Luke’s purpose in writing the Gospel (as reflected in the preface) was to prove that Christianity was nothing more than an extension of ancient Judaism: “It was therefore, essential for Luke, if he would preserve for Christians freedom from the worship of the Emperor, that he should demonstrate that Christianity was in direct genealogical succession to the religion

²³ James W. Scott, “Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem,” 388; citing, A. M. Pope, “The Key Word of the Lucan Narratives,” *The Canadian Journal of Religious Thought* 3 (1926): 48-49.

²⁴ A. M. Pope, “The Key Word of the Lucan Narratives,” *The Canadian Journal of Religious Thought* 3 (1926): 49.

of the Old Testament. And his preface, properly understood, informs us that this is the very thing he sets himself to prove.”²⁵

Despite this intriguing insight, Pope also fails to place Luke directly on the scene from the start of Christ’s ministry by choosing a lexically correct definition of ἄνωθεν, which refers to space, rather than time: “We would justify, from his own writings, our contention that Luke has in mind the early origins of Hebrew history; yea, to our evangelist, the foundation of the world is only the opening of one of the scenes in the great cosmic drama...In ἄνωθεν he has carefully selected a word which, in addition to a temporal significance, has also the connotation of *above*.”²⁶

Our thesis agrees with Pope’s exegesis concerning ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς, but we suggest that ἄνωθεν pertains directly to Luke’s firsthand experience as a disciple of Christ.

James W. Scott takes issue with scholars who have assigned the same meaning to ἄνωθεν, as they do for ἀπ’ ἀρχῆς. His analysis avoids the redundancy by defining *anōthen* as, “for a long time,”²⁷ rather than, “from the first.”²⁸ But each of these leads to quite different branches of thought. “From the first” provides support for the idea that Luke’s “knowledge started from the first, and extended to every point,”²⁹ hence, the potential for Luke having been an eyewitness to Christ’s ministry, which, according to our research, was the suggestion of only one contemporary scholar, John W. Wenham, who theorized that Luke was a disciple of Christ, more specifically he suggests that Luke was one of the seventy.³⁰

²⁵ Ibid., 46-47.

²⁶ Ibid., 48.

²⁷ James W. Scott, “Luke’s Preface and the Synoptic Problem,” 135.

²⁸ B.F. Wescott, *An Introduction to the Study of the Gospels*, Macmillan and Co. (1860), 174.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ J.W. Wenham, “Gospel Origins,” 112.

Part 2: Circular exegesis concerning the *many* blocks Luke as eyewitness

Wenham's thesis notes the circular nature of common assumptions made about the preface's proper exegesis:

The meanings of the various words in the prologue have been debated at great length. The possible interpretations are legion, and it is impossible to say that the text (considered on its own without reference to theories about the origin of the gospel) demands one particular translation. Theories of origin will ultimately govern the choices made. Some of the common assumptions about its meaning, however, need to be challenged, and an interpretation offered is here which gives a natural and precise understanding of the language used. Four negative points should first be made: (a) The prologue does not say that the "many" wrote up their material simply from what they had heard from official teachers. (2) It does not say that Luke was not an eyewitness. (3) It does not say that the tradition he had received was solely oral. (4) It does not say that Luke did not follow the events in person.³¹

The excellent point that Wenham makes here is that the Christian story has come down through the ages with common assumptions making it exceedingly difficult to have a meaningful, accurate, precise truth concerning such a monumental, but vexing biblical passage as Luke's preface, due to preconceived notions each will have. He stresses the need to focus on the actual text, rather than trying to fit one's own beliefs into it, which is exactly what Christian scholarship has done, and this is why there has been so much ink spilled over it.

James W. Scott makes a similar point, in graceful style, but then later, when dealing with a point made by Cadbury, he does an about face, and invokes his own preconceived notion in retaliation:

Almost with one voice interpreters since 1922 have been discounting the force of πολλοὶ [polloi, many] in Lk. 1:1. They have been eager to do so because Luke's "many" predecessors can thus be reduced to two or three in number, and their writings can then be identified as the two or three sources commonly held to have been used by Luke...But

³¹ Ibid., 119-120.

literary theory should not be allowed to prejudice the exegesis of Luke's preface, one way or the other. Rather, careful grammatico-historical exegesis should inform literary criticism. And, as we have seen, there are solid grounds for heeding C. K. Barrett's advice that the words of Luke's preface, including the word "many" in vs. 1, "be taken more seriously than it has of late been fashionable to take them."³²

That certainly agrees with Wenham, until Scott's thesis is confronted by prior scholarship by H.J. Cadbury, which held that the vocabulary in Luke's preface could not refer to Luke making an investigation of Gospel events, but rather the best lexical explanation was that Luke was stating that he had been part of the events unfolding:

[I]t is hard to believe that Luke would have emphasized his own personal knowledge of events after having represented himself as a recipient of the traditions of them, especially since he was not one of the special eyewitnesses who had authority to formulate tradition. The implication of vs.2 would seem to be that Luke was at best in a position only to pass on the authoritative traditions, whether or not he had witnessed anything. It must be doubted that he would then proceed to make much of what, if anything, he himself had observed...But Cadbury and almost everyone else recognized that Luke was not an observer of any of the gospel history, let alone of "all" of it. Therefore, we can hardly understand Luke to be claiming that he had kept abreast of the entire course of the gospel history.³³

Unfortunately, Scott has done the deed both he and Wenham warned about here, by making a firm assertion, as if it were a fact of the text, for which there is no direct evidence, but only circumstantial opinion, that Luke was not, and could not have been, an eyewitness to Christ. Had he taken Pope's suggestion more seriously (by avoiding the gratuitous exclamation mark³⁴), he might have had an epiphany concerning the *many*. I have immense respect for James W. Scott, and I do not intend an insult, but rather a suggestion that New Testament scholars must strive to escape the boundaries of prior scholarship, and their own biases, to better focus on the actual words that have been handed down to us, rather than what we want, or need, those words to be.

³² James W. Scott, "Luke's Preface and the Synoptic Problem," 25.

³³ *Ibid.*, 128-129.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, 376, FN 119.

Conclusion

Luke's preface has not been solved. And all scholarship available to us, from the first century until now, has been shaped by an unproven *assumption* that the preface tells us, in Luke's own hand, that he was not an eyewitness to Christ. But that's not what the text actually says, and this conclusion can only be reached by stretching his text to make the point fit. So many of the issues scholars have faced in discerning Luke's preface might be dissolved by considering that the *many* were Old Testament participants.

The issue of preconceived biases, shaped by the verbal dagger of the majority, "most scholars agree," is the biggest problem Christian scholarship faces. And it is not just concerned with Luke's preface, but all of Christian scholarship, particularly the so-called synoptic problem. John Wenham's suggestion that Luke was a witness to Christ, and one of the seventy, deserves much more attention.

Another brilliant maverick cited by Wenham, is Robert L. Lindsey, who has made an argument for Lukan priority, buttressed by the support of David Flusser:

Further impressive evidence that Luke was a Jew has come from another unexpected quarter. R. L. Lindsey was engaged in research in preparation for the translation of the gospels into modern Hebrew. Starting with no doubts about the priority of Mark and imagining "Luke as the Gentile Christian modifier of the earlier Gospel sources" (p. 26), he was astonished to find that Mark contained many non-Hebraic expressions, whereas Luke contained "almost none" and "was almost always easier to translate to idiomatic Hebrew than was Mark"... This discovery set him off on a reinvestigation of the synoptic problem, which finally led him to the belief that Luke was the first gospel. In this view he seems to have found a convert in David Flusser of the Hebrew University, Jerusalem...[T]he almost pure Hebraic character of Luke's Greek is a solid fact of the utmost importance. Not only does it show the author to be a Jew, it suggests a primitive, if not primary, source.³⁵

³⁵J.W. Wenham, "Gospel Origins," 121.

Wenham did not find Lindsey's argument for Lukan priority convincing³⁶ (but he also did not provide any substantive critique), yet he believed Lindsey's reflection on the Hebraic character of Luke's Gospel must be taken more seriously. It is entirely possible that Luke was both a Jew, and a witness to Christ.

While it is beyond the scope of this paper, there is an important candidate for the identity of Theophilus (Luke 1:4) which should be further studied, that being the High Priest of the Jewish Temple between 37-41 A.D., and for an excellent primer on this issue, I suggest the work of Richard H. Anderson, J.D., starting with, *Theophilus: A Proposal*.³⁷

Bibliography

- Alexander, Loveday. *The preface to Luke's Gospel*, Cambridge University Press (1993).
- Anderson, R.H. "Theophilus: A Proposal." *Evangelical Quarterly: An International Review of Bible and Theology* 69, no. 3 (1997): 195-216.
- Anderson, Richard. *Who are Johanna and Theophilus?: The Irony of the Intended Audience of the Gospel of Luke*, Kindle Edition. (2011). <https://www.amazon.com/Who-are-Johanna-Theophilus-Intended-ebook/dp/B0056IXW6U>
- Bauckham, Richard. *Jesus and the Eyewitnesses: The Gospels as Eyewitness Testimony*, Grand Rapids, MI, 2017.
- Bird, Michael F. "The Unity of Luke-Acts In Recent Discussion." *Journal for the Study of the New Testament* 29, no. 4 (2007): 425-448.
- Callan, Terrence. "The Preface of Luke-Acts and Historiography." *New Testament Studies* 31, no. 4 (1985): 576-581.
- Cadbury, H.J. "Commentary on the Preface of Luke." [Appendix C], in *The Beginnings of Christianity, Part i: The Acts of the Apostles*, ed. F.J. Foakes-Jackson and K. Lake (New York: Macmillan, 1920-1933): 2.489-2510.
- Cadbury, H.J. "The Knowledge Claimed in Luke's Preface." *The Expositor* 8, no. 24 (1922): 401-420.

³⁶ Ibid.

³⁷ Richard H. Anderson, "Theophilus: A Proposal," *Evangelical Quarterly: An International Review of Bible and Theology* 69, no. 3 (July-Sept. 1997): 195-215.

- Cadbury, H.J. "The Purpose Expressed in Luke's Preface." *The Expositor* 8, no. 21 (1921): 431-441.
- Cadbury, Henry J. *The Making of Luke-Acts*. S.P.C.K. (1958).
- Colson, F.H. "Notes On Luke's Preface: suggested by reading the second volume of Foakes-Jackson and Lake's Beginnings of Christianity." *Journal of theological studies* 24, no. 95 (1923): 300-309. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23950473>.
- Crimella, Matteo. "'That You May Know'. The Preface to Luke's Gospel (Lk 1:1-4)." *Biblica et Patristica Thoruniensia* 13, no. 4 (2021): 365-394. <https://doi.org/10.12775/BPTh.2020.017>.
- Dawson, Zachary K. "Does Luke's Preface Resemble a Greek Decree? Comparing the Epigraphical and Papyrological Evidence of Greek Decrees with Ancient Preface Formulae." *New Testament Studies* 65 no. 4 (October 2019): 552-571. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S002868851900016X>.
- Giambrone, Anthony. "'Eyewitnesses from the Beginning': Apologetic Innovation and the Resurrection in the Autopsy of Luke-Acts." *Revue Biblique (1946-)* 124, no. 2 (2017): 180-213. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26793979>.
- Huub, Welzen. "The Revelatory Text and the prologue of the Gospel of Luke." *HTS Theological Studies/Theologese Studies* 74, no. 3 (2018): e1-e9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v74i3.4967>
- Hunt, B.P.W. Stather. *Primitive Gospel Sources*, New York, NY: The Philosophical Library, 1951.
- James, Scott W. "Luke's Preface and the Synoptic Problem." PhD diss., St. Andrews University, 1985. <https://research-repository.st-andrews.ac.uk/handle/10023/14101>.
- Lindsey, Robert L. *Jesus Rabbi & Lord: The Hebrew Story Of Jesus Behind Our Gospels*, Oak Creek, WI: Cornerstone Publishing, 1990.
- Lindsey, Robert Lisle. *A Hebrew Translation Of The Gospel Of Mark*, Baptist Park, Jerusalem, 1969.
- Peter, John J. "Luke's Source Claims in the Context of Ancient Historiography." *Journal For The Study Of The Historical Jesus* 18 (2020): 35-60.
- Moles, John. "Luke's Preface: The Greek Decree, Classical Historiography and Christian Redefinitions." *New Testament Studies* 57, no. 4 (2011): 461-482. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0028688511000154>.
- Moessner, David P. "Luke as Tradent and Hermeneut." *Novum Testamentum* 58 (2016): 259-300.
- Pope, A.M. "The Key Word of the Lucan Narratives." *The Canadian Journal of Religious Thought* 3 (1926): 44-52.
- Robertson, A. T. "The Implications in Luke's Preface." *ExpT* 35 (1923-24):319-321.
- Wenham, J.W. "Gospel Origins." *Trinity Journal* 7, no. 2, (Fall 1978): 112-134.
- Wescott, B.F. *An Introduction to the Study of the Gospels*. Macmillan and Co. (1860).